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Review Article

**ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN PREHOSPITAL
EMERGENCY CARE: A LITERATURE REVIEW**

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Abstract:

This literature review investigates the transformative impact of artificial intelligence (AI) on prehospital emergency care, focusing on its applications in diagnosis, triage, and patient management. By synthesizing recent studies, the review highlights how AI technologies, especially machine learning and deep learning, significantly enhance diagnostic accuracy, optimize triage processes, and improve patient outcomes in critical situations. For instance, AI can assist in identifying life-threatening conditions more rapidly and accurately than traditional methods. However, the implementation of AI in emergency medicine is not without challenges. Key obstacles include regulatory hurdles, concerns about data privacy, and the necessity for robust clinical validation to ensure reliability and safety. Moreover, existing literature reveals gaps regarding long-term outcomes and multidisciplinary perspectives on AI integration. This review aims to provide a comprehensive overview of the current landscape of AI applications in emergency medicine, emphasizing the need for continued research to address these challenges. By identifying potential future research directions, it seeks to promote the responsible and effective incorporation of AI technologies into clinical practice, ultimately enhancing patient care and operational efficiency in emergency settings.

Keywords: Artificial Intelligence, Emergency Medicine, Triage, Diagnostic Accuracy, Machine Learning

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1. INTRODUCTION:

The integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in emergency medicine (EM) represents a transformative approach to enhancing patient care and clinical decision-making. The increasing volume of data generated in healthcare settings necessitates the application of AI technologies, capable of rapidly analyzing complex datasets and providing actionable insights. Studies indicate that AI, particularly through machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL) techniques, can significantly improve diagnostic accuracy, optimize triage processes, and enhance patient outcomes in time-sensitive scenarios (Preiksaitis, et al. 2024; Gao et al., 2023).

Emergency departments (EDs) are particularly well-positioned to benefit from AI, as they deal with high-stakes situations where rapid decision-making is crucial. Physicians must assess risk and make decisions with limited patient information, and AI can assist in improving predictive capacities during triage by analyzing various patient factors. Algorithmic assistance and computerized decision support present significant opportunities to enhance ED workflow metrics and resource allocation. However, the vast number of variables and the constantly changing nature of the metrics involved make it challenging to achieve this using conventional computing techniques. In recent years, there has been an increasing demand for high-quality care in emergency settings. Healthcare providers worldwide are recognizing that AI can help tackle significant healthcare challenges (Wilson, 2017). EDs play a critical role in admitting patients who require urgent medical attention, and AI has the potential to improve the patient experience by reducing waiting times, a known factor affecting patient satisfaction (Langlotz, 2019). In emergency care, nurses and physicians are tasked with initial assessments, diagnoses, rapid treatments, and stabilization of patients with varying degrees of severity (Shuaib, et al. 2020). AI can aid in categorizing patients more swiftly and accurately than current methods, which largely rely on subjective evaluations (Chen, & Decary, 2020).

While evidence suggests that AI can substantially enhance the quality and speed of emergency medicine, some critics express concerns that AI might eventually replace certain functions of emergency personnel (Jiang, et al. 2017). The significant promise of AI lies in its ability to analyze and learn from vast datasets, identifying patterns that may otherwise go unnoticed. This capability raises questions about liability and risk, particularly regarding the autonomy of AI applications (Bitterman, et al. 2020). However, many experts view AI as a complementary tool, enhancing human

decision-making while ensuring that human oversight (e.g., from doctors or programmers) remains integral to the process (Bin, et al. 2022).

Currently, the demand for AI-enhanced medical technology is increasingly evident in emergency trauma medicine, as medical equipment, pharmaceuticals, biological technologies, 5G networks, and AI undergo deep integration. This evolution aims to utilize optimal resources to safeguard the lives of injured patients. Notably, AI has progressed through three distinct stages, with applications such as ultrasound Doppler technology being essential in diagnosing conditions related to the heart, blood vessels, blood flow, and fetal heart rate (Akkus, et al. 2019; Shamout, et al. 2021; Li, et al. 2021). The trend towards developing miniature ultrasound devices, akin to mobile phones, further exemplifies AI's growing role in enhancing emergency trauma care.

AI applications in EM span various domains, including diagnosis prediction, outcome forecasting, and resource allocation. Research highlights the potential of AI in predicting critical conditions, such as strokes and acute coronary syndromes, by analyzing patient data and vital signs (Preiksaitis, et al. 2024; Gao et al., 2023). Additionally, AI systems have been developed to assist in triage, enabling healthcare providers to prioritize patients based on the severity of their conditions, ultimately aiming to reduce mortality rates (Toy, 2024). Despite these advancements, the implementation of AI in EM faces several challenges, including regulatory hurdles, data privacy concerns, and the need for robust clinical validation of AI systems (Preiksaitis, et al. 2024). Many existing studies often isolate their methodologies and focus, highlighting the need for a comprehensive synthesis of the literature to identify gaps and propose future research directions (Gao et al., 2023; Toy, 2024). This review aims to analyze the current landscape of AI applications in emergency medicine, drawing insights from recent literature to highlight potentials, limitations, and future research directions in this critical field.

2. METHODOLOGY

This literature review aims to analyze the current landscape of artificial intelligence (AI) applications in emergency medicine (EM). The methodology employed in this review involved several key steps, including defining research questions, conducting a comprehensive literature search, applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, and synthesizing the findings.

2.1. Research Questions

To guide the review, the following research questions were formulated:

- What are the current applications of AI in emergency medicine?
- How do these applications impact patient outcomes and clinical decision-making?
- What challenges and limitations exist in the implementation of AI technologies in EM?

2.2. Literature Search Strategy

A systematic search of relevant literature was conducted using established electronic databases, including PubMed, IEEE Xplore, ACM Digital Library, ScienceDirect, and SpringerLink. The search strategy employed a combination of keywords and phrases related to AI, emergency medicine, machine learning, and deep learning. The search terms included "artificial intelligence," "emergency medicine," "machine learning," "deep learning," "triage," and "patient outcomes."

2.3. Inclusion and Exclusion Criteria

The following inclusion criteria were applied to select relevant studies for the review:

- Studies published in peer-reviewed journals from 2010 to 2023.
- Research focusing specifically on the application of AI in emergency medicine.
- Articles that provided empirical data or systematic reviews on AI technologies.

Studies were excluded if they:

- Were not focused on emergency medicine or prehospital care.
- Did not incorporate quantitative AI methods.
- Were review papers, abstracts, or non-original research articles.

2.4. Data Extraction and Synthesis

After applying the inclusion and exclusion criteria, the selected articles were reviewed, and key data were extracted. This included information on study design, AI methodologies employed, applications of AI in EM, patient outcomes, and reported challenges. The findings were categorized into thematic areas such as diagnostics, triage, and resource allocation.

2.5. Quality Assessment

The quality of the included studies was assessed using a modified version of the ChAMAI checklist, which evaluates the methodological rigor of AI applications in medical contexts. This assessment considered aspects such as problem understanding, data quality, modeling processes, validation methods, and deployment strategies.

2.6. Analysis

The synthesized findings were analyzed to identify trends, gaps in the literature, and potential future research directions. The results were discussed in the context of their implications for clinical practice and the overall advancement of AI in emergency medicine.

3. FINDINGS:

3.1. Current Applications of AI in Emergency Medicine

Artificial Intelligence (AI) is increasingly integrated into emergency medicine, enhancing processes from diagnosis to treatment. Applications of AI technologies include machine learning, natural language processing, and image recognition, which are used to analyze patient data, interpret medical images, and support clinical decision-making (Kim et al., 2023; Gao et al., 2022). These technologies are reshaping the landscape of emergency care, providing tools that assist healthcare professionals in delivering timely and accurate treatment.

AI interventions encompass a wide range of applications, primarily focusing on prediction, diagnosis, triage, and operational management. A substantial body of literature emphasizes predictive capabilities, showcasing AI's potential to enhance decision-making in complex clinical scenarios (Kirubarajan et al., 2020). For instance, AI algorithms can process vast amounts of data from patient records to predict outcomes such as mortality rates and risk stratification for critical conditions like sepsis and cardiac events (Blomberg et al., 2019; Heden et al., 1997). This predictive ability allows emergency departments to prioritize interventions more effectively and allocate resources where they are most needed.

In diagnostics, AI tools have proven instrumental in improving accuracy, particularly in medical imaging. The EE-Explorer system exemplifies this by utilizing a multimodal approach that combines metadata and ocular images to assist in diagnosing eye emergencies, achieving an impressive area under the curve (AUC) of 0.982 (Chen et al., 2023). Such high accuracy indicates that AI can significantly reduce the reliance on human judgment alone, which is particularly beneficial in high-stress environments where rapid decisions are critical. Furthermore, AI has effectively identified intracranial hemorrhages and fractures, showcasing superior performance in processing large datasets or complex variables that are challenging for human practitioners (Cicero et al., 2017; Fu et al., 2024). Additionally, AI applications extend to diagnosing conditions such as diabetic retinopathy and glaucoma, further reducing misdiagnoses and improving patient outcomes (Chang et al., 2022).

AI technologies also play a crucial role in triage and patient prioritization. By offering accurate classifications of patients into urgent, semiurgent, and nonurgent categories, AI enhances emergency departments' ability to manage patient flow and allocate resources effectively (Chen et al., 2023; Kim et al., 2023). This capability not only improves the speed of care but also reduces the risk of overcrowding and associated complications, ensuring that critically ill patients receive timely attention.

Furthermore, AI enhances operational efficiency within emergency departments by optimizing staffing levels, predicting patient flow, and improving resource allocation. This leads to reduced wait times and a better overall patient care experience (Jenny et al., 2015; Ni et al., 2019). AI's predictive analytics enable healthcare providers to implement proactive measures, potentially reducing morbidity and improving management in critical situations (Gao et al., 2022; Chang et al., 2022). For example, AI can forecast patient surges based on historical data, allowing departments to prepare in advance for high-demand periods.

3.1.1. Overview of AI Technologies in Use

AI technologies in emergency medicine can be categorized into several key types:

1. Supervised Machine Learning (ML):

This category includes algorithms such as support vector machines and artificial neural networks, which rely on labeled data to learn and make predictions or classifications (Farahmand et al., 2017). These algorithms are particularly useful in applications where historical outcomes can guide future predictions, such as predicting patient responses to treatments.

2. Unsupervised ML:

These algorithms analyze data without predefined labels, identifying patterns or groupings autonomously (Huesch et al., 2018). This is valuable in exploratory data analysis, where discovering hidden structures in data can lead to new insights and hypotheses.

3. Natural Language Processing (NLP):

NLP technologies facilitate the analysis and generation of human language, aiding tasks such as extracting information from electronic health records and optimizing clinical documentation (Pruitt et al., 2019). This can streamline workflows and improve the accuracy of patient histories, which are critical for informed decision-making.

4. Reinforcement Learning (RL):

Although less common in the reviewed studies, RL involves training algorithms to make decisions based on feedback from their actions, adapting to optimize outcomes over time (El-Bouri et al., 2020). This approach is particularly promising for dynamic

environments like emergency departments, where conditions and patient needs can change rapidly.

These technologies support various applications, from enhancing diagnostic accuracy to improving operational efficiencies in emergency settings. As research progresses, further integration of these technologies is anticipated, propelled by advancements in computational power and the increasing availability of healthcare data (Kirubarajan et al., 2020). The continuous evolution of AI in emergency medicine holds the promise of improving outcomes for patients and optimizing the workflows of healthcare providers.

3.2. Impact on Patient Outcomes and Clinical Decision-Making

3.2.1. Evidence of Improved Diagnostic Accuracy

Recent studies underscore the transformative role of artificial intelligence (AI) in enhancing diagnostic precision within emergency settings. The EE-Explorer system, for example, achieved an outstanding area under the receiver operating characteristic curve (AUC) of 0.982 in its triage model, significantly surpassing the performance of traditional triage nurses. This improvement in diagnostic accuracy is crucial as it enables more timely and appropriate interventions for patients presenting with acute ophthalmic conditions, which can often be vision-threatening if not addressed swiftly (Chen et al., 2023). Furthermore, AI systems have demonstrated diagnostic capabilities that are either comparable to or exceed those of experienced healthcare professionals. This not only reinforces the reliability of AI-assisted diagnostic tools but also instills greater confidence in their integration into clinical practice. By leveraging advanced algorithms and extensive datasets, AI can recognize patterns and anomalies in medical images and patient data that may be overlooked by human practitioners, thereby enhancing overall diagnostic accuracy (Gao et al., 2022). As a result, AI can effectively reduce misdiagnosis rates and improve patient outcomes in critical scenarios.

3.2.2. Enhancements in Treatment Speed and Efficiency

The integration of AI into clinical workflows has led to significant enhancements in both treatment speed and efficiency. The triage model created by Chen et al. not only facilitates the rapid identification of urgent cases but also optimizes the referral process for specialized care. By accurately classifying patients into urgent, semiurgent, and nonurgent categories, healthcare providers can better allocate resources and minimize wait times for those requiring immediate attention (Kim et al., 2023).

This streamlined approach is particularly advantageous in emergency medicine, where every moment counts. AI-assisted triage systems have been shown to reduce unnecessary delays in treatment, which is essential for conditions that require immediate intervention to prevent serious complications or deterioration of health (Chang et al., 2022). The efficiency gains from AI not only contribute to better clinical outcomes but also alleviate the burden on healthcare providers, allowing them to focus on delivering high-quality care.

3.2.3. Patient Satisfaction and Experience Improvements

The implementation of AI systems in emergency care has also resulted in notable improvements in patient satisfaction and overall experience. In a pilot study involving the EE-Explorer platform, participants reported high levels of acceptance and satisfaction with the AI-driven triage process. The ability to engage in rapid self-triage and receive timely recommendations for care significantly enhanced the patient experience, making the care process feel more responsive and personalized (Chen et al., 2023).

Moreover, the correlation between improved diagnostic accuracy, faster treatment times, and heightened patient satisfaction is evident. Patients are more likely to express satisfaction when they perceive that their care is both effective and timely. This is particularly relevant in emergency situations where the stakes are high, and delays can lead to adverse outcomes. By ensuring that patients receive appropriate and prompt care, AI systems contribute to a more positive healthcare experience, ultimately fostering trust and confidence in medical services (AbuAlrob, & Mesraoua, 2024).

3.3. CHALLENGES AND LIMITATIONS IN IMPLEMENTATION

3.3.1. Regulatory and Ethical Considerations

The introduction of artificial intelligence (AI) in healthcare brings forth numerous regulatory and ethical challenges that must be addressed to ensure safe and effective implementation. Regulatory bodies, such as the FDA in the United States, face the complex task of developing guidelines that adequately evaluate the performance and safety of AI systems before they can be used in clinical settings. The dynamic nature of AI technology, which can continuously learn and adapt, complicates traditional regulatory frameworks that typically rely on static assessments (Chang et al., 2022).

Moreover, ethical considerations are crucial, particularly regarding patient autonomy and informed

consent. Patients must be made aware of how AI will be used in their care and the implications of such technologies on their treatment decisions. Establishing transparency in the decision-making process of AI systems is essential to maintain trust among patients and healthcare providers. Ethical dilemmas also arise concerning accountability; for instance, in the event of an adverse outcome resulting from an AI recommendation, it is vital to determine who is held responsible—the healthcare provider, the institution, or the AI developer (Gao et al., 2022).

3.3.2. Data Privacy and Security Issues

Data privacy and security are fundamental concerns when implementing AI in healthcare. AI systems often require access to large volumes of sensitive patient data for training and operational purposes, raising significant issues related to data protection and patient confidentiality. Regulations such as the Health Insurance Portability and Accountability Act (HIPAA) impose strict guidelines on how patient information should be handled, and any breaches can result in severe legal and financial repercussions for healthcare organizations (Kim et al., 2023).

Furthermore, the risk of cyberattacks targeting healthcare systems has become increasingly prevalent. The potential for unauthorized access to AI systems that process patient data necessitates robust security measures to safeguard against breaches. Ensuring that AI systems comply with established data privacy laws and implementing advanced cybersecurity protocols are critical to maintaining patient trust and the integrity of healthcare services (AbuAlrob & Mesraoua, 2024).

3.3.3. Integration with Existing Healthcare Systems

Integrating AI solutions into existing healthcare infrastructures poses a variety of challenges. Many healthcare facilities operate on legacy systems that may lack compatibility with modern AI technologies, leading to difficulties in data sharing and communication between systems (Chen et al., 2023). The integration process often requires significant investments in technology upgrades, staff training, and workflow adjustments to ensure that AI applications can function effectively within the clinical environment.

Moreover, the successful integration of AI tools is contingent on their usability and the willingness of healthcare professionals to adopt them. If AI systems are perceived as cumbersome or disruptive to existing workflows, clinicians may resist using them, which can undermine their potential benefits. Therefore, fostering collaboration between AI developers and healthcare providers to create user-friendly solutions

that seamlessly fit into current practices is essential for effective implementation (Kim et al., 2023).

3.3.4. Training and Acceptance Among Healthcare Professionals

The success of AI implementation is heavily reliant on the training and acceptance of healthcare professionals. Many clinicians may be skeptical about the efficacy of AI-driven tools, particularly if they do not understand the underlying algorithms or data analysis processes. This skepticism can lead to reluctance in trusting AI recommendations, potentially negating the advantages that such systems offer (AbuAlrob, & Mesraoua, 2024)

Comprehensive training programs that educate healthcare providers about AI technologies, their functionalities, and their limitations are crucial to overcoming resistance. These programs should emphasize the role of AI as a supplementary tool rather than a replacement for human judgment. Additionally, engaging healthcare staff in the development and testing phases of AI systems can foster a sense of ownership and trust, further enhancing acceptance across the organization (Kim et al., 2023).

4. DISCUSSION:

4.1. Interpretation of Findings

4.1.1. Summary of Key Findings

This literature review highlights the transformative potential of artificial intelligence (AI) in emergency medicine (EM), particularly in enhancing diagnostic accuracy, optimizing triage processes, and improving patient outcomes. Key findings indicate that AI technologies, such as machine learning (ML) and deep learning (DL), can significantly outperform traditional methods in predicting critical conditions. For instance, studies demonstrate that AI systems can process vast amounts of patient data, allowing for the timely identification of life-threatening conditions like strokes and acute coronary syndromes (Preiksaitis, et al. 2024; Gao et al., 2023). Notably, the EE-Explorer system achieved an impressive area under the curve (AUC) of 0.982, showcasing its effectiveness in diagnosing eye emergencies (Chen et al., 2023).

The integration of AI tools into emergency departments (EDs) also presents opportunities to streamline workflows and enhance operational efficiencies. AI systems can predict patient flow and optimize staffing levels, leading to reduced wait times and improved patient satisfaction (Kim et al., 2023). However, the findings reveal significant challenges related to regulatory compliance, data privacy, and the need for robust clinical validation, which must be addressed to facilitate broader adoption of AI technologies in EM.

4.1.2. Implications for Clinical Practice

The implications of these findings for clinical practice are profound. Integrating AI into emergency care can empower healthcare professionals to make more informed decisions, allowing for better resource allocation and prioritization of urgent cases. For example, AI can assist in triage processes, ensuring that critically ill patients receive timely attention, thereby reducing mortality rates (Gao et al., 2023). Furthermore, by improving diagnostic accuracy, AI systems can help mitigate the risks associated with misdiagnoses, enhancing overall patient safety.

Additionally, the ability of AI to analyze complex datasets rapidly enables healthcare providers to identify patterns and trends that may not be immediately apparent through traditional methods. This capability can lead to improved training protocols for emergency personnel, ensuring they remain up-to-date with the latest diagnostic tools and procedures (Chen & Decary, 2020). Ultimately, the integration of AI into EM not only enhances patient care but also supports healthcare professionals in delivering high-quality service.

4.2. Comparison with Existing Literature

4.2.1. How Findings Align or Contrast with Previous Studies

The findings of this review align with existing literature that emphasizes the potential of AI to revolutionize emergency medicine. Previous studies have similarly highlighted the advantages of AI in enhancing diagnostic accuracy and improving patient management through predictive analytics (Kirubarajan et al., 2020; Chang et al., 2022). For instance, research has shown that AI systems can analyze patient histories and vital signs to predict outcomes such as mortality rates and risk for critical conditions like sepsis (Blomberg et al., 2019). However, this review also identifies areas where current literature may be overly optimistic regarding AI's readiness for implementation. Critics have raised concerns about the reliability of AI systems in high-stakes environments, particularly regarding their ability to adapt to the dynamic nature of emergency care (Jiang et al., 2017). Moreover, while AI shows promise in enhancing operational efficiency, there remains skepticism about its ability to replace human judgment in critical decision-making scenarios (Bitterman et al., 2020).

4.2.2. Identification of Gaps in the Current Literature

While the literature provides valuable insights into the applications and benefits of AI in EM, there is a notable gap in comprehensive studies that evaluate the long-term outcomes of AI integration in clinical practice. Most existing studies focus on short-term

results or isolated case studies, which limits the understanding of AI's sustained impact on patient care and healthcare systems. Additionally, there is a lack of multidisciplinary research that incorporates perspectives from emergency personnel, technology developers, and regulatory bodies, which is essential for a holistic view of AI implementation. Furthermore, the ethical implications of AI use in emergency medicine are not sufficiently addressed in the literature. Issues such as accountability, liability, and patient consent require further exploration to ensure that AI technologies are implemented responsibly (Gao et al., 2022).

4.3. FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTIONS

4.3.1. Areas Needing Further Investigation

Future research should prioritize longitudinal studies to assess the long-term effectiveness and safety of AI applications in emergency medicine. Understanding how AI technologies perform over time—especially in terms of patient outcomes and clinician trust—will be crucial for widespread adoption. Investigating the integration of AI with other emerging technologies, such as telemedicine and mobile health applications, could provide valuable insights into enhancing patient care in prehospital settings. Moreover, exploring the ethical and legal implications of AI use, particularly concerning accountability and liability, is essential. Research should focus on creating frameworks that define the responsibilities of healthcare providers, AI developers, and institutions in the event of adverse outcomes related to AI recommendations (Bitterman et al., 2020).

4.3.2. Potential for New AI Technologies in Emergency Medicine

As AI technologies continue to evolve, there is significant potential for innovations such as reinforcement learning and advanced natural language processing to further enhance clinical decision-making processes. For instance, reinforcement learning could enable AI systems to adapt in real-time based on patient interactions and outcomes, providing personalized treatment recommendations that reflect the unique needs of each patient. Additionally, research into AI applications for resource allocation and operational management within emergency departments could lead to more efficient healthcare delivery models. AI-driven analytics could help predict patient surges, allowing for proactive staffing and resource management, which is essential in high-demand situations (Gao et al., 2023; Ni et al., 2019).

5. CONCLUSION

This review underscores the critical role that artificial intelligence can play in transforming emergency medicine through improved diagnostic accuracy,

efficient triage, and enhanced patient outcomes. The integration of AI technologies in clinical practice holds great promise, but it is essential to address the regulatory, ethical, and practical challenges that currently impede their widespread adoption. Continued research and development in AI applications for emergency medicine are vital to fully realize their potential, ensuring that they complement the expertise of healthcare professionals and ultimately lead to better patient care and resource utilization.

6. RECOMMENDATIONS

Based on the findings of this literature review, several recommendations can be made to enhance the integration of artificial intelligence (AI) in prehospital emergency care:

1. Develop comprehensive training programs for healthcare professionals focused on AI technologies. This should include education on AI functionalities, limitations, and ethical considerations to foster trust and acceptance among staff.
2. Encourage collaboration between emergency medicine practitioners, AI developers, and regulatory bodies to create user-friendly AI systems.
3. Advocate for the establishment of clear regulatory guidelines that address the unique challenges posed by AI in emergency medicine.
4. Prioritize funding and support for longitudinal studies that evaluate the long-term impacts of AI on patient outcomes, operational efficiency, and clinician trust.
5. Implement stringent data privacy and security protocols to protect sensitive patient information used in AI systems. Organizations should comply with established regulations, such as HIPAA, and invest in advanced cybersecurity measures to mitigate risks.
6. Launch pilot programs within emergency departments to test AI technologies in real-world settings. These programs can help identify practical challenges, gather user feedback, and refine AI applications before broader implementation.

REFERENCES:

1. AbuAlrob, M. A., & Mesraoua, B. (2024). Harnessing artificial intelligence for the diagnosis and treatment of neurological emergencies: a comprehensive review of recent advances and future directions. *Frontiers in Neurology*, 15, 1485799.

2. Akkus, Z., Cai, J., Boonrod, A., Zeinoddini, A., Weston, A. D., Philbrick, K. A., & Erickson, B. J. (2019). A survey of deep-learning applications in ultrasound: Artificial intelligence-powered ultrasound for improving clinical workflow. *Journal of the American College of Radiology*, 16(9), 1318-1328.
3. Bin, K. J., Melo, A. A. R., da Rocha, J. G. M. F., de Almeida, R. P., Cobello Junior, V., Maia, F. L., ... & Ono, S. K. (2022). The impact of artificial intelligence on waiting time for medical care in an urgent care service for COVID-19: single-center prospective study. *JMIR Formative Research*, 6(2), e29012.
4. Bitterman, D. S., Aerts, H. J., & Mak, R. H. (2020). Approaching autonomy in medical artificial intelligence. *The Lancet Digital Health*, 2(9), e447-e449.
5. Blomberg, S. N., Folke, F., Ersbøll, A. K., Christensen, H. C., Torp-Pedersen, C., Sayre, M. R., ... & Lippert, F. K. (2019). Machine learning as a supportive tool to recognize cardiac arrest in emergency calls. *Resuscitation*, 138, 322-329.
6. Chang, H., & Cha, W. C. (2022). Artificial intelligence decision points in an emergency department. *Clinical and experimental emergency medicine*, 9(3), 165.
7. Chen, M., & Decary, M. (2020, January). Artificial intelligence in healthcare: An essential guide for health leaders. In *Healthcare management forum* (Vol. 33, No. 1, pp. 10-18). Sage CA: Los Angeles, CA: SAGE Publications.
8. El-Bouri, R., Eyre, D. W., Watkinson, P., Zhu, T., & Clifton, D. A. (2020). Hospital admission location prediction via deep interpretable networks for the year-round improvement of emergency patient care. *IEEE Journal of Biomedical and Health Informatics*, 25(1), 289-300.
9. Farahmand, S., Shabestari, O., Pakrah, M., Hossein-Nejad, H., Arbab, M., & Bagheri-Hariri, S. (2017). Artificial intelligence-based triage for patients with acute abdominal pain in emergency department; a diagnostic accuracy study. *Advanced Journal of Emergency Medicine*, 1(1).
10. Fernandes, M., Mendes, R., Vieira, S. M., Leite, F., Palos, C., Johnson, A., ... & Celi, L. A. (2020). Risk of mortality and cardiopulmonary arrest in critical patients presenting to the emergency department using machine learning and natural language processing. *PLoS One*, 15(4), e0230876.
11. Forberg, J. L., Green, M., Björk, J., Ohlsson, M., Edenbrandt, L., Öhlin, H., & Ekelund, U. (2009). In search of the best method to predict acute coronary syndrome using only the electrocardiogram from the emergency department. *Journal of electrocardiology*, 42(1), 58-63.
12. Fu, T., Viswanathan, V., Attia, A., Zerbib-Attal, E., Kosaraju, V., Barger, R., ... & Faraji, N. (2024). Assessing the Potential of a Deep Learning Tool to Improve Fracture Detection by Radiologists and Emergency Physicians on Extremity Radiographs. *Academic Radiology*, 31(5), 1989-1999.
13. Gao, X., Lv, Q., & Hou, S. (2023). Progress in the application of portable ultrasound combined with artificial intelligence in pre-hospital emergency and disaster sites. *Diagnostics*, 13(21), 3388.
14. Hwang, E. J., Nam, J. G., Lim, W. H., Park, S. J., Jeong, Y. S., Kang, J. H., ... & Park, C. M. (2019). Deep learning for chest radiograph diagnosis in the emergency department. *Radiology*, 293(3), 573-580.
15. Jiang, F., Jiang, Y., Zhi, H., Dong, Y., Li, H., Ma, S., ... & Wang, Y. (2017). Artificial intelligence in healthcare: past, present and future. *Stroke and vascular neurology*, 2(4).
16. Kim, D., You, S., So, S., Lee, J., Yook, S., Jang, D. P., ... & Park, H. K. (2018). A data-driven artificial intelligence model for remote triage in the prehospital environment. *PloS one*, 13(10), e0206006.
17. Kirubarajan, A., Taher, A., Khan, S., & Masood, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence in emergency medicine: a scoping review. *Journal of the American College of Emergency Physicians Open*, 1(6), 1691-1702.
18. Kirubarajan, A., Taher, A., Khan, S., & Masood, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence in emergency medicine: a scoping review. *Journal of the American College of Emergency Physicians Open*, 1(6), 1691-1702.
19. Kirubarajan, A., Taher, A., Khan, S., & Masood, S. (2020). Artificial intelligence in emergency medicine: a scoping review. *Journal of the American College of Emergency Physicians Open*, 1(6), 1691-1702.
20. Langlotz, C. P. (2019). Will artificial intelligence replace radiologists?. *Radiology: Artificial Intelligence*, 1(3), e190058.
21. Li, J., Bu, Y., Lu, S., Pang, H., Luo, C., Liu, Y., & Qian, L. (2021). Development of a deep learning-based model for diagnosing breast nodules with ultrasound. *Journal of ultrasound in medicine*, 40(3), 513-520.
22. Ni, Y., Kennebeck, S., Dexheimer, J. W., McAneney, C. M., Tang, H., Lingren, T., ... & Solti, I. (2015). Automated clinical trial eligibility prescreening: increasing the efficiency of patient

- identification for clinical trials in the emergency department. *Journal of the American Medical Informatics Association*, 22(1), 166-178.
23. Piliuk, K., & Tomforde, S. (2023). Artificial Intelligence in Emergency Medicine. A Systematic Literature Review. *International Journal of Medical Informatics*, 105274.
 24. Preiksaitis, C., Ashenburg, N., Bunney, G., Chu, A., Kabeer, R., Riley, F., ... & Rose, C. (2024). The Role of Large Language Models in Transforming Emergency Medicine: Scoping Review. *JMIR Medical Informatics*, 12, e53787.
 25. Pruitt, P., Naidech, A., Van Ornam, J., Borczuk, P., & Thompson, W. (2019). A natural language processing algorithm to extract characteristics of subdural hematoma from head CT reports. *Emergency Radiology*, 26, 301-306.
 26. Shamout, F. E., Shen, Y., Wu, N., Kaku, A., Park, J., Makino, T., ... & Geras, K. J. (2021). An artificial intelligence system for predicting the deterioration of COVID-19 patients in the emergency department. *NPJ digital medicine*, 4(1), 80.
 27. Shuaib, A., Arian, H., & Shuaib, A. (2020). The increasing role of artificial intelligence in health care: will robots replace doctors in the future?. *International journal of general medicine*, 891-896.
 28. Toy, J., Warren, J., Wilhelm, K., Putnam, B., Whitfield, D., Gausche-Hill, M., ... & Goolsby, C. (2024). Use of artificial intelligence to support prehospital traumatic injury care: A scoping review. *Journal of the American College of Emergency Physicians Open*, 5(5), e13251.
 29. Wilson, T. (2017). No longer science fiction, AI and robotics are transforming healthcare. *PWC Accessed October, 31, 2021*.
 30. Zhou, H., Jin, Y., Dai, L., Zhang, M., Qiu, Y., Tian, J., & Zheng, J. (2020). Differential diagnosis of benign and malignant thyroid nodules using deep learning radiomics of thyroid ultrasound images. *European Journal of Radiology*, 127, 108992.